

MICROSCOPIC DAMAGE EVOLUTION OF BOLT JOINT IN CARBON FIBER REINFORCED METAL LAMINATE

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1 Introduction

Fiber metal laminates (FMLs) are hybrid composite materials that laminate metal and fiber-reinforced plastics (FRP) alternately. Glare that laminates glass fiber reinforced plastics and an aluminum alloy (Al) is successfully adopted as an upper fuselage panel in an Airbus A380.

Recently, Research Institute for Applied Mechanics, Kyushu University succeeded in an autoclave molding of carbon fiber-reinforced metal laminates CFMLs by applying a new coating comprised of a sulfuric acid anodizing and a silica nano-particle reinforced hybrid sol-gel coating [1]. It also proposed a cure process to decrease thermal stresses drastically. The damage evolution of a pin joint was studied microscopically [2]. This paper presents the results of microscopic damage analysis of a [Al/0/90]_s CFML bolt joint.

2 Experimental Procedures

Dimensions of a coupon specimen are as follows, length = 150, width $w = 30$, thickness = 1.9, edge distance = 30 and hole diameter = 6.

A single hole double lap joint test was conducted by

a 100kN MTS testing machine with a cross head speed of 0.5mm/min in tension. Specimens are loaded to obtain load-stroke curves first and next for damage analysis. At the latter case the loading machine is set to unload quickly after it detects the decrease of load more than 50 to 200N, which keeps microscopic damage features at the load peak by avoiding the overlap of additional damage driven by the stored energy in the specimen and fixture.

The damaged specimen is cut out into pieces at the bearing plane and the piece is impregnated with epoxy, cured and polished for careful investigation by an optical microscope.

3 Results and Discussions

Figure 1 shows a typical load-stroke curve of a bolt joint together with previous results of a pin joint. After the gradual increase of gradient the curve shows the linear increase up to around 4kN, and passing the linear limit a gradual decrease of gradient is observed. At around 6.5kN a larger change of gradient appears which is termed as knee point. After a small magnitude of up and down

Fig.1 Load-stroke curves of mechanical joint.

Fig.2 50-200N drop points for test pieces used in microscopic damage analysis

followed by two piecewise almost linear parts, the maximum load point is reached and the final stage starts. The curve shape around knee point is similar to the one of a pin at 5 to 5.5kN. The maximum load appears at 9kN and 6kN with stroke of 2mm and 0.5 to 1mm for bolt and pin, respectively. Figure 2 shows points from which test pieces for the microscopic damage analysis are obtained after rapid unloading.

Figure 3 presents microscopic damages of a bolt at both knee point and final stage. (a) Around knee point there is multiple kink perpendicular to loading axis, no shear matrix crack in 90° layer and straight Al plate. The 0° layer and Al plate support a load of 6.5kN. (b) Two Al plates cannot open freely, which affords a bolt a high resistance of 7.8kN.

Figure 4 of a pin case presents (a) lateral bending expansion in Al, shear matrix crack in 90° layer, and single shear type or multi kink with large deformation at the maximum load point and (b) yielding with intense bending deformation in Al.

It seems that damages at knee point of a bolt joint correspond to that of the maximum point of a pin case. Though out of plane damage initiation or propagation occurs in a pin joint, it does not in a bolt case, which leads to high load resistance of a bolt joint of CFML. Lateral constraint has two effects, that is, continuation of two linear segments, by enclosing the damaged zone within a closed region, which

results in the small increase of knee point load and large increase of the maximum load.

References

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(a) Damages around knee point

(b) Final failure stage

Fig.3 Microphotographs of the bearing failure of a bolted joint.

(a) Damage around the maximum load

(b) Final failure stage

Fig.4 Microphotographs of the bearing failure of a pinned joint.